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"The Concept of Boundary Disputes in Smriti Literature"

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Abstract:

The paper explores boundary disputes in Smriti literature, focusing on ancient Hindu legal texts like Manu Smriti and Yajnavalkya Smriti. It elucidates methods for resolving disputes, types of boundaries, guidelines for territorial construction, the role of feudal lords, rules for dispute resolution, the significance of witnesses, and permissions in unique circumstances. Through nuanced perspectives from ancient sages like Manu, Katyayana, and Narada, the texts provide a comprehensive framework for adjudicating conflicts and fostering communal harmony. Key themes include boundary delineation, witness testimony, pragmatic governance, and shared resource utilization, offering timeless insights into justice and stewardship. These insights remain relevant for navigating contemporary boundary disputes, ensuring equity and harmony in society.

Keywords:

Boundary Disputes, Smriti Literature, Ancient Hindu Law, Witness Testimony.

Introduction

Dharmashastra, an esteemed genre of Sanskrit texts and Shastra, stands as a cornerstone in Hinduism, embodying religious precepts and legal duties. This intricate scholarly tradition epitomizes a profound system deeply ingrained within the fabric of Hindu society. Its profound legal intricacies have garnered attention, to the extent that early British colonial rulers recognized Dharmashastra as the governing law for Hindus in India. Among the multifaceted array of subjects it addresses, boundary disputes emerge as a significant matter of contention, constituting one of the eighteen causes delineated within its vast expanse. Thus, delving into the concept of boundary disputes within Smriti Literature unveils not only legal intricacies but also sheds light on the cultural and societal ethos embedded within ancient Indian civilization.

What is a Boundary Dispute?

The term "Seema" denotes "Boundary" in Sanskrit. Within Smriti literature, the method for resolving border disputes between two towns or families is meticulously outlined. Manu, a revered sage and lawgiver, offers his perspective on settling such disputes in his seminal work, the Manu Smriti.

Manu suggests that when a dispute arises between two towns regarding their boundaries, the presiding judge should undertake the task of delineating the boundary line. He stipulates that this adjudication should occur during the Jestha month, a period typically marked by the complete drying up of grass and vegetation due to the sun's intense heat. Manu advocates for this specific timing as it ensures optimal visibility, allowing for the clear demarcation of the boundary line. The verse from Manu Smriti elucidates this guidance:

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"सीमां प्रति समुत्पन्ने विवादे ग्रामयोर्द्वयोः।

ज्येष्ठे मासि नयेत्सीमां सुप्रकाशेषु सेतुषु॥¹

Here, Manu advises that in the event of a dispute arising between two villages regarding their boundaries, the judge should ascertain the boundary line during the Jestha month, particularly amidst the brilliantly illuminated boundary markers. Manu's counsel reflects a pragmatic approach to boundary dispute resolution, emphasizing the importance of optimal conditions for accurate determination. By aligning the decision-making process with the natural environment's cues, Manu underscores the significance of precision and clarity in establishing territorial boundaries.

Types of Territorial Boundaries

When disputes arise concerning the boundaries of villages or the delineation of fields within a single village, the parties involved must await the emergence of boundary markers to assist in determining the precise boundary. Yajnavalka, another revered sage and jurist, expounds upon the various types of territorial boundaries in Smriti literature, enumerating four distinct categories: Janapada Seema, Village Seema, Kshetra Seema, and Griha Seema. Each category is further elaborated upon with five specific methods of determination.

Yajnavalka elucidates the characteristics of these boundaries, employing descriptive terms to aid in their identification. For instance, he describes Dhvagini, which resembles flags on trees, and Matsini, denoting watery places. Naidhani signifies buried materials such as paddy husk or charcoal, while Bhayavarjita indicates boundaries established through mutual agreement, devoid of fear or apprehension. Rajashasani delineates boundaries decreed by the authority of the king.

The text also mentions various physical landmarks designated as boundary markers. These include lakes, wells, temples, gardens, pits, streams, bushes, mountains, and others. These landmarks serve as tangible demarcations, ensuring clarity and permanence in the determination of territorial boundaries.

The verse from Smriti literature encapsulates the essence of these boundary markers and their significance in boundary delineation:

"ध्वजिनीमत्स्यिनी चैव नैधानी भयवर्जिता।

राजशासननीता च सीमा पञ्चविधा स्मृता॥²

वापीकूपतटाकानि चेत्यारामसुरालयाः।

स्थलनिम्नदीप्तोतः शरगुल्मनगादयः॥

प्रकाशचिह्नान्येतानि सीमायां कारयेत्सदा॥³

This verse underscores the multifaceted nature of boundary delineation, highlighting the importance of both natural and man-made landmarks in ensuring clarity and fairness in territorial disputes.

Manu's Guidelines for Territorial Construction

In the ancient text of Manu Smriti, sage Manu provides profound insights into the construction and preservation of territorial boundaries, emphasizing the importance of meticulous planning and thoughtful implementation. His teachings serve as a timeless blueprint for fostering order and harmony within communities.

Manu advises the strategic cultivation of various trees and plants, including, Ashwattha, Palasha, cotton, incense, palm, and milky fig trees, along the border areas. Additionally, he advocates for the planting of small shrubs, bamboos, bunnies, vines, and bushes, complemented by the construction of sturdy logs to demarcate boundaries effectively. Central to Manu's vision is the notion that the demarcation line should remain indelible, ensuring clarity and permanence.

तडागान्युदपानानि वाप्यः प्रस्रवणानि च।

सीमासन्धिषु कार्याणि देवतायतनानि च॥⁴

The sage further recommends the establishment of significant landmarks at the junctions of village boundaries. Lakes, wells, water canals, temples, and other structures serve as tangible symbols of territorial limits, fostering a sense of community identity and shared responsibility. Moreover, Manu underscores the importance of creating subtle identification marks to mitigate potential confusion among residents regarding border delineations.

Manu's guidance extends to the burial of various non-perishable materials within the demarcated area, including rocks, bones, cattle hairs, chaff, ashes, fragments of broken pots, iron, bricks, charcoal, gravel, sand, and other materials. These buried markers serve as additional reference points, reinforcing the boundaries against encroachment or dispute.

अश्मनोऽस्थीनि गोवालांस्तुषान् भस्म कपालिकाः।

करीषमिष्टकाङ्गारान् शर्करा बालुकास्तथा॥⁵

In the process of determining different types of boundaries, such as Janapada Seema, Village Seema, Kshetra Seema, and Griha Seema, Manu emphasizes the significance of recognizing and interpreting boundary features. Stones, trees, charcoal, ashes, and other natural or

man-made symbols serve as essential indicators, guiding vassals tasked with resolving disputes. Disputes that persist beyond local adjudication are to be escalated to the king for final resolution, ensuring equitable outcomes for all parties involved.

Role of Feudal Lords in Settlement of Border Disputes

Feudal lords numbering 4, 8, 10, and so forth, were selected equitably from neighboring villages. Identified by their attire, adorned with red flower garlands and with a piece of earth on their heads, they were tasked with delineating the territory. In their absence, the elders assumed this responsibility. These appointed feudal lords were expected to possess impeccable character and virtue. Swearing by the witnesses, they were entrusted with delivering a just verdict. Should they fail to reach a consensus, a revered religious figure, agreeable to both parties, could effectively resolve the boundary dispute.

Rules Governing Dispute Resolution

When disputes arise in the determination of boundaries, the guidance from ancient texts provides clarity. Narada's View:

अथ चेदनृतं ब्रूयुः सामन्ताः सीमनिर्णये।

सर्वे पृथक् पृथक् दण्ड्याः राज्ञा मध्यम साहसम्॥⁶

"In the event of false claims in the determination of boundaries, the king was instructed to levy fines, amounting to 540 panas, upon each erring vassal. Initial transgressors were also subject to penalties."

Yajnavalkya's Opinion:

अनृते तु पृथक्-पृथक् दण्ड्याः, राज्ञा मध्यमसाहसम्।

अभावे ज्ञातुचिह्नानां राजा सीमः प्रवर्तिता॥⁷

"Similarly, when discrepancies in witness testimonies occurred, fines were to be levied upon each offender. The king, guided by moderate action, assumes the responsibility of executing these penalties."

Role of Witnesses in Boundary Disputes

In the resolution of boundary disputes, the determination of boundaries relied heavily on markers buried by the king. These markers served as crucial indicators, bridging the gap between the disputing parties and the longstanding occupants of the area.

Even in the presence of various overt and covert signs of identification, if the boundary remained undecided, recourse to evidence became necessary for resolution. Witnesses, summoned before the townspeople, played a pivotal role. Their testimony, presented in the presence of both plaintiffs and defendants, underwent thorough examination regarding boundary marks.

On such occasions, the names of all witnesses, along with the details concerning the decision on boundaries provided by them, were meticulously recorded.

Manu's Perspective:

यथोक्तेन नयन्तस्ते पूयन्ते सत्यसाक्षिणः।

विपरीतं नयन्तस्तु दाप्याः स्युद्विशतं दमम्॥⁸

"According to Manu, witnesses, when they speak the truth as stated, purify; but if they speak falsely, they shall suffer a twofold punishment."

Witnesses were required to swear an oath of truthfulness in front of the judge. If their testimony was accepted as truthful, they were revered as saints. However, bearing false witness incurred a penalty of 200 Panas. In cases where witnesses were unavailable for boundary determination, the four village chiefs, representing the nearest villagers, were tasked with consulting and deciding the boundary in the presence of the king.

In the absence of villagers able to testify, the judge could interrogate forest dwellers, such as Bedars, fowl catchers, cowherds, fishermen, herb sellers, Snake charmer, Saints, and others engaged in forest occupations, to clarify village boundaries.

Manu's Insight:

ते पृष्टास्तु यथा ब्रूयुः सीमासन्धिषु लक्षणम्।

तत्तथा स्थापयेद्राजा धर्मेण ग्रामयोर्द्वयोः॥⁹

"Manu suggests that the judge must impartially establish the boundary of both villages according to the explanation given by all parties involved in the matter of boundary."

Manu's Directive:

क्षेत्रकूपतडागानामारामस्य गृहस्य च।

सामन्तप्रत्ययो ज्ञेयः सीमासेतु विनिर्णयः॥¹⁰

"Manu directs that while determining the boundaries of fields, wells, lakes, gardens, plantations, and houses within the same town, decisions should be based on the statements provided by nearby residents. In the event of disputes among them regarding boundaries, fines must be imposed on each party if they are found to be lying."

In this manner, the involvement of witnesses and their truthful testimony, as per Manu's teachings, played a crucial role in resolving boundary disputes, ensuring impartial judgment, and clarity in delineating boundaries.

Determination of Various Boundaries

The vassals were required to be knowledgeable about the distinguishing features of lands, water sources such as wells, lakes, pits, recreational areas, residences, etc., which fostered the growth of fruits and flowers. Similarly, they had to adhere to regulations concerning the flow of

rainwater passing through the middle of their residences. Disputes regarding palaces, buildings, and other structures were to be resolved accordingly.

A modest piece of land demarcating the boundaries of multiple fields was termed as 'Maryada'. In cases of transgression against these regulations, fines of varying degrees, namely Adham, Medium, and Adventure, were to be imposed based on the severity of the offense. For instance, if someone encroached upon a field under the false belief that it belonged to them, or did so deliberately, a fine of 200 Panas would be levied. In instances where the number of transgressors was minimal, an Adventure penalty was prescribed.

Trespassers who encroached upon houses, fields, lakes, or gardens out of fear, intimidation, or ignorance were to be fined according to the nature of their offense.

Katyayana's View:

तडागोद्यान तीर्थानि यो मेध्येन विनाशयेत्।
अमेध्यं शोधयित्वा तु दण्डयेत् पूर्वसाहसम्॥¹¹

According to Katyayana, one who destroys or damages sacred water bodies, parks, or pilgrimage sites should be punished accordingly. If the act was unintentional, a search for amends must be made, followed by a fine equivalent to the first offense.

Manu's Insight:

गृहं तडागमारामं क्षेत्रं वा भीषया हरन्।
शतानि पञ्च दण्ड्यः स्यादज्ञानाद्विशतो दमः॥¹²

Manu elucidates that when disputes over boundaries persist despite the involvement of witnesses and other indicators, the judge should personally investigate the matter and impartially allocate the disputed area to the party that would derive the most benefit from it.

Permissions in Unique Circumstances

In the midst of foreign territories, the construction of bridges and dams should not face prohibition, for even minor faults are overshadowed by the significant benefits they bring.

Yajnavalkya's Perspective:

परक्षेत्रस्य मध्ये तु सेतुर्न प्रतिषिध्यते।
महागुणोज्ज्वल्य दोषश्चेत् वृद्धिरिष्टा क्षये सति॥¹³

"Within foreign domains, bridges and dams must not be prohibited, as their considerable advantages outweigh minor flaws in the face of potential growth."

Similarly, the installation of wells and lakes should not be impeded, despite their small footprint, as they offer copious water. However, actions leading to substantial losses for meager gains warrant prohibition.

Yajnavalkya's view :

स्वामिने योऽनिवेद्यैव क्षेत्रे सेतुं प्रवर्तयेत्।
उत्पन्ने स्वामिनो भोगस्तदभावे महीपते॥¹⁴

"Should a bridge or dam arise in someone else's land without notifying the landowner or king, the builder bears no liability for its outcomes; instead, the responsibility falls upon the landowner or king. Therefore, such undertakings necessitate prior permission from the landowner or king."

Shared Rights in Border Areas

Amidst the borderlands, where trees straddle the boundaries of two territories, the fruits and flowers of such trees are to be designated as common property among the respective landowners.

Narada's Perspective:

सीमामध्ये तु जातानां वृक्षाणां क्षेत्रयोर्द्वयोः।
फलं पुष्पं च सामान्यं क्षेत्रस्वामिषु निर्दिशेत्॥
अन्यक्षेत्रे तु जातानां शखा यत्रान्य संस्थिताः।
स्वामिनं तं विजानीयाद्यस्य क्षेत्रेषु संस्थिताः॥¹⁵

"In the midst of border areas, the trees born on the boundary should yield their fruits and flowers for the common benefit of the landowners. However, in cases where the branches of a tree extend into another's territory while its roots remain within a different land, the landowner of the territory where the roots lie shall rightfully enjoy the tree's fruits."

Conclusion:

In the intricate tapestry of ancient legal systems, the resolution of boundary disputes stood as a testament to the importance of meticulous observation, judicious interpretation, and equitable adjudication. From the insightful directives of Manu and the practical wisdom of Katyayana to the nuanced perspectives of Narada, the texts provided a comprehensive framework for delineating borders, settling conflicts, and fostering communal harmony.

Witnesses played a pivotal role in this process, their testimony serving as the bedrock upon which just decisions were built. Through their eyes, the truth emerged, guiding judges in impartially assigning rights and responsibilities.

Furthermore, special cases, such as the construction of bridges and the shared use of resources, reflected a pragmatic approach to governance, emphasizing the balance between individual rights and collective welfare.

In essence, these ancient texts offer timeless insights into the principles of justice, cooperation, and stewardship of the land. By honoring these principles, societies past and

present continue to navigate the complexities of boundary disputes, ensuring the preservation of harmony and the pursuit of equity for all.

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